

19th century taxonomy and the invisible skeleton of the Ward Project and Ward's Natural Science Establishment

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Ward's Natural Science Establishment of Rochester New York played a central role in the early development of natural history education, collections, and museums. By the late 1880s, Ward's had sold materials to approximately 250 institutions, 69 of which remain active, and still hold and display those specimens. The Ward Project (wardproject.org) presents specimens, correspondence, catalogs (some annotated), invoices and personal diaries from the collections in the Department of Rare Books and Special Collections at the University of Rochester. Taken together, this material chronicles in detail the unmatched growth of the natural history movement in the last half of the 19th century. The website design uses the Darwin Core and Dublin Core metadata standards to facilitate data sharing with the biodiversity community. It is a virtual museum that invites those outside University of Rochester to add images of specimens, documents and other relevant materials, and to transcribe letters.

Taxonomy and perceived evolutionary relationships were a central component of the cabinets that Ward's Natural Science Establishment sold, but many of the names of the organisms in those cabinets are outdated, misspelled, and not accepted today. This talk discusses the importance of the scientific names of organisms to the Ward Project's structure and cohesiveness: its invisible skeleton. We use the Specify program to link the taxonomic changes of a name to the currently accepted name and have developed a program that allows us to populate the Taxonomic tree in Specify with synonyms linked to their accepted names we download from GBIF. Connecting currently accepted taxonomy to those 19th century names used in price lists, catalogs, letters, and specimen labels helps users to seamlessly collate information on specimens in their own collections.

